

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 3.2 Develop the website

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

This is a Horizon Europe project (Coordinated and Support Action) funded by the European Union for 3 years (from 1 July 2022 until 30 June 2025).

Project summary

Support Stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9.

The overarching goal of this project is to bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platforms (ETIP ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan.

Supporting the alignment and efficient coordination of stakeholders – including industry, researchers, public authorities, civil society – in order to accelerate the delivery of the CCUS research and innovation (R&I) activities and to progress the emerging policy priorities at EU and national level for the implementation of CCUS, will be crucial over the coming years for Europe to reach the ambitious climate targets for 2030 and 2050.

This will be achieved by efficiently aligning and coordinating the activities of ETIP ZEP and the IWG9 in a joint work programme; establishing networks and other fora to enable the stakeholders to collaborate and coordinate effectively, pooling expertise, experience and resources to address common challenges; engaging also with other programmes and external stakeholders; facilitating engagement and creating greater interaction and cohesion between the different CCUS activities; supporting the CCUS community to develop clear strategies and recommendations; accompanied by a strong continuous programme for outreach, dissemination and communication.

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Deliverable 3.2: Develop the website

Description: to be used for dissemination, communication and as a repository for all information generated by the project, freely available for all also beyond the project's lifetime.

There was a need to update the ZEP website in order to freely disseminate as much information as possible from the work in an easily accessible way, regarding functionality, design, and layout as well as content display and accessibility. Given the coordination between ETIP ZEP and the IWG9, there was also a need to connect the two websites to help the user with access and searchability. The websites also include information generated by previous projects supporting the Zero Emissions Platform (ETIP ZEP) and the SET-Plan Implementation plan working group on CCUS (IWG9).

2 WEBSITE DEVELOPMENTS

2.1 General setup

The objective of the website development is to make the ZEP homepage more engaging, more easily accessible – both functionality and design – to create a repository for previous and current grant documents and to connect the ZEP and IWG9 websites for easy access:

- More informative and content-driven homepage,
 - Slider with key reports, timely news, events and Network/working group meetings – with link to specific page,
 - Clearly shown 'Highlights and Latest news',
 - Simpler Menu structure,
 - More visible European Commission disclaimer – Grant information,
- Easily accessible link between the ZEP and IWG9 websites, and to keep as much as possible of the IWG9 (IMPACTS9) website.
- Increased searchability.
- Better analytics tool to keep track of website traffic.

2.2 Technical / functional updates

Technical changes made in order to increase accessibility, responsiveness, and searchability for users, and to ensure long-term technical robustness also beyond the project's lifetime:

- Adjusted **responsiveness** of the website.
- Technical **back-office adaptations**.

- **Improved search function** – The user is able to find the information they are looking for easier and quicker.
- **Easier and more direct access to content.**
- **Improved background analytic tool** to monitor usage and performance.
- Improvement and **interlinkage between the ZEP and IWG9 websites.**
- **Enhanced readability on mobile phones** – All updates made with responsiveness in mind – for both desktop and mobile.

3 ZEP HOMEPAGE AND MENU LAYOUT

<https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/>

ZEP is supported by the European Union and receives funding from Horizon Europe (grant n°101075790)

About Discover CCS and CCU News and resources Contact Us CCUS SET Plan Stakeholders Area

The Zero Emissions Platform

ZEP is a European Technology and Innovation Platform under the European SET-Plan, acting as the adviser to the European Union on the deployment of CCS and CCU.

ZEP's broad membership base – from Oil&Gas, Industry, Utilities and Equipment suppliers, to Research, trade unions, and environmental NGOs – results in balanced views and recommendations, making ZEP a trusted organisation to liaise with the European Institutions and cooperate with Member State governments.

ZEP also coordinates actively with many other initiatives on national, European and international level.

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ZEP's objectives are threefold

Determine and create the conditions necessary to reach net-zero GHG emissions in Europe by 2050 with a focus on energy and industrial sectors.

Demonstrate that the implementation of CCS and CCU technologies at scale now is essential to achieve this goal.

Accelerate the deployment of large-scale CO₂ transport and storage networks, enabling clean, competitive energy and industrial sectors, early large-scale clean hydrogen, and carbon dioxide removal.

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To make net-zero possible we need

An enabling policy framework – making it economically feasible to invest in all parts along the CCUS value chain.

Strong continued support for CCUS R&I through Horizon Europe and partnerships.

Coherent and coordinated EU and national funding programs.

An EU strategy for CCS and CCU – including a regulatory framework for CO2 transport infrastructure.

Markets for net-zero products – where real climate impact is reflected in the price.

ZEP is supported by the European Union and receives funding from Horizon Europe (grant n°101075790)

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The Net-Zero Industry Act proposal

The Zero Emissions Platform welcomes the European Commission's proposal for the Net-Zero Industry Act. The proposal comes as a landmark political recognition of the contribution of CCS and CCU technologies to Europe's climate neutrality target.

It is poised to provide a predictable and simplified regulatory environment and stronger incentives for net-zero industries in the EU, making it essential to act swiftly to get the regulation adopted.

See ZEP's reaction to the proposal here

[SEE PROPOSAL](#)

ZEP is the adviser to the EU on the deployment of Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) and Carbon Capture and Utilisation (CCU) – a European Technology and Innovation Platform (ETIP) under the Commission's Strategic Energy Technologies Plan (SET-Plan). CCS and CCU will be essential for the European transition to net neutrality, ensuring that power generation and industrial processes are secure, reliable and sustainable

Latest News

ZEP paper on the Green Deal Industrial Plan and the Net-Zero Industry Act

The Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP) has published a new paper titled 'ZEP paper on the Green Deal Industrial Plan and the Net-Zero Industry Act'. This paper outlines the key challenges and opportunities for the industrial sector in achieving net-zero emissions by 2050. It highlights the need for a strong policy framework, including a regulatory framework for CO2 transport infrastructure and markets for net-zero products. The paper also emphasizes the importance of continued support for CCUS R&I through Horizon Europe and partnerships, and the need for coherent and coordinated EU and national funding programs. The paper is available for download on the ZEP website.

[ZEP paper on the Green Deal Industrial Plan and the Net-Zero Industry Act](#)

[ZEP paper on the Green Deal Industrial Plan and the Net-Zero Industry Act](#)

Highlights

<p>ZEP paper on the Green Deal Industrial Plan and the Net-Zero Industry Act</p>	<p>ZEP reaction to the Net-Zero Industry Act</p>	<p>Response to the call for feedback on the EU certification framework for carbon removals</p>
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Changes made, content driven:

- Clearer indication of the **EU Grant and number**, moved to top of each page.
- **Better visibility of ZEP logo**, moved to top left, and reduced menu height.
- **Menus simplified**, reorganised and text descriptions added on drop down menus:
 - Menu **About** now includes description of the **Zero Emissions Platform, Membership, Who we are, and Privacy Policy**.

- Menu **Discover CCS and CCU** includes **Why CCS** is crucial, descriptions of **What is CCS** and **What is CCU** (Capture, Transport, Utilisation, and Storage), and the map of CCS/CCU Projects.

- Menu **News and resources** includes **Reports** with better search functionality, **Positions** and **Consultations**, **News**, **Events**, and the searchable **Archive** with better search functionality.

- Menu **Contact us** with new map.
- Menu **CCUS SET Plan** that links to the IWG9 homepage.
- Homepage top: **Slider with most important items** (Change every month – start: conference), mid: **Latest news** item, Low: **Content highlights**. Bottom: **Twitter**, **LinkedIn**, **Newsletter**, **Contact information**.

4 IWG9 / CCUS SET-PLAN HOMEPAGE AND MENU LAYOUT

<http://www.ccus-setplan.eu/>

The screenshot shows the homepage of the CCUS SET-PLAN website. At the top left is the CCUS SET-PLAN logo. To its right is a navigation menu with the following items: "About SET-Plan", "Project and Resources" (with a dropdown arrow), "News & Events" (with a dropdown arrow), and "ZEP website". The main content area has a dark blue background with a starry pattern. The title "CCUS SET-PLAN" is displayed in large, bold, light green letters. Below the title is a white text block containing a mission statement: "Combatting climate change is one of the biggest challenges of our time. Europe is taking a leading role and aims at an economy with net-zero greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 2050. Europe's energy and industrial sectors can contribute to this goal by adopting low-carbon technologies at large scale." Below this is a smaller white text block explaining the goal of the European Strategic Energy Plan (SET-Plan) and the role of Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage (CCUS).

The screenshot shows the "About SET-Plan" page. The navigation menu is identical to the homepage. The page title "About SET-Plan" is in white on a dark blue background. The main content area is white. On the left, there is a green text block: "The European Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET Plan) is a European initiative that has been launched in 2007 by the European Commission." Below this is a paragraph: "It aims at accelerating the development and deployment of low-carbon technologies, through cooperation amongst EU countries, companies, research institutions, and the EU". On the right, there is a section titled "SET-PLAN ACTIONS" in green. Below the title is a paragraph: "The Integrated SET-Plan identifies ten priority actions that could serve help accelerate the energy system transformation and the realisation of the EU's aim to become the global leader in the deployment and use of renewable energy". Below this is a numbered list of 10 actions:

1. Performant renewable technologies integrated in energy system
2. Reduce costs of technologies:
3. New smart technologies and services for consumers
4. Resilience and security of the energy system
5. New materials and technologies for energy efficiency solutions for buildings:
6. Energy efficiency for industry:
7. Competitive in global battery sector and e-mobility
8. Renewable fuels and bioenergy:
9. Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage
10. Nuclear Safety

About SET-Plan Project and Resources ▾ News & Events ▾ ZEP website

Grant period July 2019 – June 2022

IMPACTS9 was a Horizon 2020 project (Coordinated and Support Action) funded by the European Commission for 3 years (from 1st May 2019 until 28th February 2022).

Its purpose was to accelerate the progress realised within the CCUS SET-Plan and to support delivery of the R&I activities in the CCUS Implementation Plan.

This goal has been achieved by

- > Supporting **coordination** of the CCUS sector and strengthening of **partnerships** between national, EU, industrial and academic stakeholders.
- > Rationalising and increasing the public and private **funding sources** needed for delivery of the CCUS R&I activities and monitoring their delivery.
- > Preparing the **framework conditions** for an accelerated deployment of CCUS technologies.
- > Supporting **dissemination and communication** of the delivery of the CCUS SET-Plan targets.
- > Ensuring cross-thematic **coordination** with the Implementation Plans established to deliver the **other SET Plan targets**.

SEARCH PUBLICATIONS

BY TYPE

WORKSHOPS

13 SEPTEMBER 2022

5.9 – Summary report on CCUS integration in

WORKSHOPS

13 SEPTEMBER 2022

5.8 – Final report on dissemination and

About SET-Plan Project and Resources ▾ News & Events ▾ ZEP website

Grant period July 2022 – June 2025

CURRENT PROJECT

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

- > A 3-year (1 July 2022 – 30 June 2025) Coordinated and Support Action Horizon Europe project funded by the European Union.
- > SINTEF Energy is the Coordinator for the project.
- > The Carbon Capture and Storage Association ASBL is the Secretariate and leads the work of the project.

The overarching goal of this project is:

- > To bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platform (the Zero Emissions Platform, ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan.
- > To support the alignment and efficient coordination of stakeholders – including industry, researchers, public authorities, civil society – in order to accelerate the delivery of the CCUS research and innovation activities and to progress the emerging policy priorities at EU and national level for the implementation of CCUS, will be crucial over the coming years for Europe to reach the ambitious climate targets for 2030 and 2050.

Changes made:

- Menus are simplified and reorganised: **About SET-Plan, Project and Resources, News & Events, ZEP website.**
- Menu **Project and Resources** includes the choice of **Grant period 2019-2022** – holding information about the previous project IMPACTS9 and all documentation from the project – and **Grant period 2022-2025**, where documents from the current grant can be stored as soon as they are approved by CINEA, increasing accessibility and searchability. Searchability by type – **Workshops, Newsletter, Report** – has been included to increase accessibility.
- In order to keep the previous information and link to the latest updates, the menu **News & Events** has a dropdown function showing 1) **News & Events** – referring to the ZEP website News and Events section, 2) **News archive** – referring to the news during the previous grant, and 3) **Events archive** – referring to the events during the previous grant.
- Menu item **ZEP website** included to increase accessibility.